

Manuscript: JMTP MS 13-0927-736.

**Green Shades: A Segmentation Approach Based on Ecological Consumer Behavior
in an Emerging Economy**

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The marketing principles known as green marketing (e.g., Kalafatis et al. 1999; McDonagh and Clark 1995; Ottman, Stafford, and Hartman 2006; Peattie and Charter 1997; Peattie and Crane 2005) have evolved over recent decades and will continue to do so as larger numbers of consumers worldwide become more concerned about the importance of protecting the natural environment. As the new century unfolds, green marketing will continue to develop and provide marketing practitioners, academics, and society with new opportunities.

However, it is not clear how green marketing can be integrated into existing marketing concepts in the context of different cultural values and economies (Amine and Smith 2009; Quelch and Jocz 2008; Vargo and Lusch 2004). Thus, this research seeks to investigate green consumer behavior in Mexico, an important emerging economy with substantial environmental challenges but also huge potential for green innovations and improvements.

In high-income countries (HIC), environmental concern has grown substantially in importance, from a focus on energy conservation and pollution in the 1960s to environmental responsibility in the '70s and '80s, while the 1990s were referred to as the “decade of the environment” (Brown and Wahlers 1998; Carlson, Grove, and Kangun 1993; McDaniel and Rylander 1993; McDougall 1993; Menon et al. 1999; Prothero 1996).

From 2000 onward, social and environmental issues have become increasingly important for consumers when making purchasing decisions. As a consequence, marketers had to adapt to newly-evolving consumer segments and purchasing patterns and accurately assess how their marketing-mix decisions affect the environment.

Recent research demonstrates that green marketers and policy makers are faced with a substantial amount of heterogeneity in environmentally-friendly behaviors (Dolnicar and Grün 2009). That is, important differences may exist between consumers in their behaviors related to the natural environment and also in their underlying values and attitudes. Thus, Schlegelmilch, Bohlen, and Diamantopoulos (1996, p. 35) suggest that “in order to position their green product offerings, companies must first segment the market according to levels of pro-environmental purchase behavior and then target the ‘greener’ consumer segments.” However, it remains unclear whether consumer segments identified in developed countries do equally exist in emerging economies. Further, it may be dangerous to conclude that segmentation variables used in research in developed countries may differentiate between segments the same way as in emerging economies. This study contributes to the knowledge gap in emerging economies by presenting the results from a market segmentation study of 715 consumers from the three most important urban centers in Mexico (Guadalajara, Monterrey, and Mexico City). The importance of Mexico is underlined by forming part of the ten emerging and growth leading economies (EAGLEs) which are forecasted to lead global growth for the next ten years (Wassener 2010). Further, several banks and professional services, including Goldman Sachs and PricewaterhouseCoopers Economics, predict that Mexico will become the world’s fifth-largest economy by 2050. The focus on important urban centers in Mexico (as opposed to the countryside) is based on the observation that important environmental problems tend to manifest in the bigger cities of emerging economies rather than in rural areas. For example, despite intents to curb Mexico City’s air pollution, particulate matter with an aerodynamic diameter less than 10 μm (PM_{10}) and ozone levels are still far above Mexican air quality standards and remain a serious threat for public health (Bell et al. 2006). Thus, this study represents one of the few

attempts to segment consumers in an emerging economy according to their pro-environmental behaviors, and (to our best knowledge) it is the first to do so in Mexico, Latin America's second biggest economy.

Our study is informed by previous qualitative research from Carrete et al. (2012) who show that environmentally-friendly behaviors in Mexico seem to be ingrained in the traditional heritage of savings and frugality rather than based on strong environmental values.

However, the authors find an important amount of heterogeneity in the Mexican consumer market for green behaviors as well as the underlying motivations and attitudes toward the environment. For example, whereas some of their informants demonstrated environmentally-friendly behaviors based on an authentic commitment for the natural environment, a second group of more affluent consumers seemed to participate in recycling and green product purchasing predominantly in an effort to emulate lifestyles from developed countries, whereas a third segment of "bottom-of-the-pyramid" consumers engaged in reducing, re-using, and recycling as their predominant means of saving money.

Building on the importance of distinguishing between different types of environmentally-friendly behaviors, our research considers the three Rs (reducing, reusing, and recycling; Inami 2001) as bases for our market segmentation of the Mexican consumer. Further, we add a fourth environmentally-friendly behavior, the purchase of products labeled as ecological, biological, or organic (Gupta and Odgen 2009; Husted et al. 2014). The resulting segments are described based on important demographic variables, such as gender, age, education, marital status, and income. However, previous research suggests that the relationship between demographic variables and environmental behaviors may be limited (Diamantopoulos et al. 2003). Thus, this study adds to previous research by profiling the resulting segments based on general social and specific environmental values

(Gilg, Barr, and Ford 2005) and perceived consumer effectiveness (Roberts 1996; Straughan and Roberts 1999).

Our study contributes to previous research on green consumer behavior in two ways. First, our segmentation approach takes into account different combinations of environmentally-friendly behaviors. Thus enabling marketing practitioners and policy makers to identify segments that seem to be similar in their overall engagement with the natural environment, but are fundamentally different when considering specific environmental behaviors such as reducing, reusing, recycling, and the purchase of green products. For example, we identified two segments in our study that have similar aggregated scores of ecological behaviors, but differ substantially in their combination of specific behaviors. Specifically, whereas the eco-fashion segment scored high on recycling and the purchase of green products, but lower on reducing and reusing, the eco-saver segment scored high on reducing and reusing, but lower on recycling and the purchase of green products.

Understanding these underlying patterns of behavior can help marketers and policy makers to develop effective marketing mix strategies. Second, our findings suggest that environmental behaviors may be related not only to altruistic motives, as demonstrated in previous research (Clark, Kotchen, and Moore 2003; Straughan and Roberts 1999), but also to egoistic motivational forces. Thus, our study provides marketing practitioners and academics with an enhanced understanding of the composition and structure of different consumer segments with respect to pro-environmental behaviors and attitudes in the context of an emerging economy.

DEMOGRAPHICS, VALUES, AND PERCEIVED CONSUMER EFFECTIVENESS IN GREEN MARKETING: AN OVERVIEW

Demographics

Previous research investigating the relationship between demographic variables and environmental behaviors reports mixed results (Buttel and Taylor 1992; Carson and Moulden 1991; Diamantopoulos et al. 2003; Scott and Willits 1994; Stern et al. 1995; Straughan and Roberts 1999). For example, some authors found younger consumers to be more environmentally-friendly (Chen et al. 2013; Samdahl and Robertson 1989). However, Roberts (1996) found older people to be more environmentally-friendly, and some authors failed to find a significant relationship (Clark et al. 2003; Jain and Kaur 2006). Similarly, research testing the relationship between income and environmental behaviors does not provide clear results. Whereas some authors found that consumers with middle and high incomes show more pro-environmental behaviors than lower-income consumers (Clark et al. 2003), other studies suggest that income is not a predictor for pro-environmental behavior (Chan 1996; Jain and Kaur 2006).

With regard to gender, several studies reported that women tend to show more pro-environmental behaviors than men (Chen et al. 2013; Diamantopoulos et al. 2003; Eagly 1987; Jain and Kaur 2006; Roberts 1995; Samdahl and Robertson 1989). However, other studies found that men have a more thorough understanding of environmental issues and more positive attitudes toward the purchase of green products (Arcury and Johnson 1987; Mostafa 2007a), and some authors (Eagles and Muffit 1990) were unable to discern any gender-based differences related to pro-environmental attitudes. Finally, one might expect educational level to be a more accurate yardstick of attitudes towards the environment than other demographic variables. However, previous research fails to demonstrate a conclusive

relationship between attitudes toward the environment and education. Although some authors reported a positive relationship between attitudes toward the environment and level of education (Bodur and Sarigöllü 2005; Chen et al. 2013; Finisterra do Paco and Barata Raposo, 2010; Roberts 1996), Samdahl and Robertson (1989) found a negative correlation between these two variables.

Values

Research on values has either concentrated on the direct effect of values on environmental behaviors (Fraj and Martinez 2006; Gutiérrez 1996; Thøgersen and Olander 2002) or on their indirect effect (McCarty and Shrum 1993; Stern et al. 1995, 1999; Thøgersen and Grunert-Beckmann 1997). These studies have been conducted predominantly in high income countries characterized for their forward-thinking policies, relatively high levels of education, and environmental consciousness. Less is known about the relationship between values and environmentally-friendly behaviors in emerging economies.

With respect to studies related to the direct effect of values on environmentally friendly behaviors, previous research suggests that values influence behaviors differently. That is, not all values are equally relevant when attempting to explain different pro-environmental consumer behaviors (Gutiérrez 1996). Further, values seem to have an indirect effect on environmentally-friendly behaviors through the mediation of beliefs, personal norms, attitudes, and environmental consciousness. For example, Grob (1995) and Stern et al. (1999) propose models in which values are the departure points which generate, among others, consciousness about the consequences of one's actions, an attitude that in turn triggers pro-environmental behaviors. This sequence of variables has been tested empirically to explain, for example, energy-conservation behaviors in emerging economies

(Ibtissem 2010). In terms of attitudes, the hierarchical relationship between values, attitudes, and behaviors has been clearly demonstrated (Chan 2001; Dembkowski and Hanmer-Llyod 1994; Kim 2011; McCarty and Shrum 1993, 1994; Thøgersen and Grunert-Beckmann 1997).

Concerning the types of values which have the most important influence on consumers' pro-environmental behaviors, academics have frequently taken as a baseline pioneering studies such as the Rokeach Value Survey (1973) or the Schwartz Value Survey (1992). Stern et al. (1999) proposed the following values for their model of Values-Norms-Beliefs: biospheric, social/altruistic, and egoistic. Biospheric values (equivalent to the Schwartz "natural" subtype of self-transcendence) are related to concerns about the protection of non-human species and the biosphere. Social or altruistic values (equivalent to the Schwartz "general" subtype of self-transcendence) represent concern for the well-being of others, and egoistic values (equivalent to "self-enhancement") represent principles oriented toward oneself. The authors argue that biospheric and social-altruistic values influence environmentally friendly behaviors positively, whereas the influence of egoistic values is negative.

Congruent with these findings, previous research showed a positive influence of biospheric values, universalism, and benevolence on environmentally friendly behaviors such as recycling and waste reduction (Thøgersen and Grunert-Beckmann 1997; Thøgersen and Olander 2002). In developing countries, Chan (2001) and Kim (2011) confirmed a positive effect of collectivist values on pro-environmental attitudes and green purchasing behaviors. Furthermore, Chan (2001) demonstrated the effect of human-nature cultural orientation (equivalent to an eco-centric orientation) on intentions and the purchase of green products in China.

Multicultural studies, such as those from Schultz and Zelezny (1998) conducted in Mexico, Nicaragua, Peru, Spain, and the U.S., revealed a positive relationship between values, awareness of the consequences for environmental damage, ascribed responsibility, and pro-environmental behaviors. This clearly indicates that values, and particularly the “nature” subtype of self-transcendence, are important variables to consider in the prediction of environmental behaviors. Thus, previous research suggests that values are important for understanding green consumers in high income countries, but also in developing economies where individuals are typically less conscious about environmental issues.

Perceived consumer effectiveness

Following Ellen, Wiener, and Cobb-Walgren (1991), we define perceived consumer effectiveness as the domain-specific belief that the efforts of an individual can make a difference in the solution of a problem. Although the development of theory related to perceived consumer effectiveness (PCE) has not been as extensive as that concerning values, PCE has received significant attention as a valid construct able to distinguish between high and low ecologically conscious consumers (Finisterra do Paco, Barata Reposo, and Leal Filho 2009; Lee and Holden 1999 ; Straughan and Roberts 1999). Additionally, among the variables examined as an antecedent to environmentally friendly behavior, PCE has been found to have the highest explanatory power in several studies (Awad 2011; Kinnear, Taylor, and Ahmed 1974; Oliver and Rosen 2010; Roberts 1996; Straughan and Roberts 1999; Webster 1975).

Ellen et al. (1991) found that PCE makes a unique contribution to the prediction of several environmentally conscious behaviors, such as green purchasing, recycling, and support of green civic organizations. Roberts (1996) and Straughan and Roberts (1999) determined

that PCE is the most important predictor variable, explaining a substantial portion of the variance in ecologically conscious consumer behavior (ECCB). Kim and Choi (2005) investigated the direct and interaction effects of PCE, collectivism, and environmental concern on ecological purchasing. Their research demonstrated that collectivist values impact perceived self-efficacy, which in turn influences green buying behavior. In the context of an emerging economy, Lee (2008) identified PCE as an important factor in motivating engagement in green purchasing behavior.

Conceptual model

Given the scarcity of green segmentation studies in emerging economies, the purpose of this research is to identify ecological/non-ecological consumer segments based on their type and strength of environmental behavior. Contrary to previous research that has focused primarily on demographic segmentation variables, we explicitly include social and environmental values and the perceived effectiveness of environmentally friendly behaviors in our study to describe the segments. The conceptual framework that informs our segmentation study is based on hierarchy-of-effects models such as the knowledge-attitudes-behavior (KAB) model (Flamm 2006, Kaiser, Wölfing, and Fuhrer 1999). Specifically, demographic variables, values, and perceived consumer effectiveness are modeled as antecedents for environmentally-friendly behaviors such as reducing, reusing, recycling, and the purchase of green products. However, our data analysis follows a top-down approach by first segmenting Mexican consumers based on their pro-environmental behaviors and in a second step profiling the segments based on demographics, values, and PCE (Figure 1). As a result, we obtain segments with richer descriptions that allow marketers to target pro-environmental segments with more precision and provide policy

makers with more information about those segments that lag behind with specific environmental behaviors.

[Place Figure 1 About Here]

METHOD

Survey instrument

The survey consisted of four sections with several multi-item scales that were adapted from prior research (see the Appendix for an itemized list of the scales). Except for social values, which were measured with five-point rating scales ranging from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (very important), all items were measured with five-point Likert-style scales ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Because the original scales were in English, we translated all items into Spanish using the parallel-blind translation technique (Behling and Law 2000). Specifically, two of the principal researchers of this study who are fluent in both English and Spanish were translating the questionnaire simultaneously and independently of each other. The resulting two versions in Spanish were then compared and discrepancies resolved by discussion. Subsequently, the questionnaire was tested in a pilot study with 60 participants in order to identify and eliminate potential problems.

We measured environmental behaviors with eleven five-point, Likert-style items based on the Roberts' (1996) ECCB scale. The scale includes items related to reusing, reducing, recycling, and the purchase of green or organic products. Perceived consumer effectiveness was measured with four five-point, Likert-style items adopted from Roberts (1996) and Straughan and Roberts (1999). Because the pilot study indicated problems with the wording of two of the items and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) produced poor results for the complete four-item scale, we removed the two problematic items (see the Appendix for the

two remaining items).

Environmental values were measured with the ten-item, five-point environmental value (EV) scale from Gilg, Barr, and Ford (2005). Finally, we measured social values based on the Gilg et al. (2005) social values (SV) scale. The original SV scale has 16 five-point items; however, one item relating to respect for diverse lifestyles (varied life) was eliminated, because it proved to be problematic in the pilot study. Specifically, although the intention of the question was to gain an understanding of the acceptance of a wider range of lifestyles, many participants interpreted this item as being related to sexual preferences.

Sample

Because larger cities in emerging economies (as opposed to the countryside) usually represent the most substantial impact on the natural environment, we collected data from the general population in the three most important urban centers in Mexico: Mexico City, Guadalajara, and Monterrey. A market research agency administered 300 questionnaires in each of the three locations for a sample frame of 900 respondents. Participants were invited to answer the survey at public places such as shopping malls or parks.

In order to represent important population characteristics adequately in the sample, we applied quota for gender and income. Table 1 shows the gender and income distribution for the overall Mexican population (INEGI 2010) and the sample. Although the sample is slightly biased towards higher-income consumers, it represents the overall population quite well. Concerning age and education, 6% of the respondents were younger than 18 years, 25% were between 18 and 25 years, 20% were between 26 and 33 years, 14% were between 34 and 41 years, 14% were between 42 and 49 years, 11% were between 50 and 58 years, and 6% were 58 years or older. Further, 8% indicated elementary school as their

highest level of education, followed by middle school (31%), undergraduate degree (30%), postgraduate degree (3%), technical studies (4%), and other studies (1%). Concerning memberships in environmental groups such as Green Peace, 3.5% of the respondents reported to belong to such an interest group. Because towards the end of the study, some consumers who were willing to participate had to be rejected in order to fill the quotas, we do not report a response rate. Out of these 900 responses, 185 were eliminated, as they were incomplete, resulting in a total of 715 valid surveys.

[Place Table 1 About Here]

RESULTS

Scale validity and reliability

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was used in a first step to determine the factor structure and dimensionality of the measurement scales. KMO values for the four scales were above 0.7, and the Bartlett Sphericity tests were significant ($p < .001$), indicating that the conditions for conducting an exploratory factor analysis were met. The exploratory factor analysis for the environmental behaviors (EB) scale produced three factors which, congruent with our expectations, relate to reducing, reusing, and recycling and the purchase of green products. We removed one item (“I buy products that have less packaging”) from the scale due to crossloadings and a communality below .4, thus reducing the total number of scale items from 11 to 10. A revision of the problematic item led us to the conclusion that participants most probably did not perceive less packaging as being more environmentally friendly. As explained in the Survey Instrument section, we kept two of the four original items from the perceived consumer effectiveness (PCE) scale after conducting the pilot study. The two items demonstrated substantial factor loadings (0.81).

The environmental values (EV) scale was reduced from 10 to the 8 items. One of the items we eliminated (“There are no limits to growth for nations like Mexico”) is a negatively worded item, which we assume is the reason it loaded on a separate factor (Barnette 2000). The second item that was removed (“The earth has limited area and resources”) is a double-barreled item and had very low factor loadings. After purifying the scale, the items loaded on three factors (anthropocentrism, biospherism, and science and technocentrism), as suggested by Gilg et al. (2005). Finally, two items from the social values (SV) scale (“enjoying life” and “social order”) had substantial crossloadings and communalities below 0.4. We thus decided to remove these items from the scale. The remaining 13 items grouped into four factors (altruism, openness to change, conservatism, and egoism) and replicated the original factor structure from Gilg et al. (2005), as expected.

Internal consistency (Cronbach alpha) was acceptable for all scales except for the PCE scale and two of the three subscales from the EV scale. However, Cronbach alpha is a lower bound estimate of reliability and based on the assumption of tau-equivalence. If this assumption is violated or the number of test items is very small, alpha will underestimate reliability (Graham 2006). Thus, we base our reliability assessment on composite reliability rather than Cronbach alpha. Composite reliability was above the cut-off value of 0.6 for scales administered in a country different from the original context (Nunnally 1978) and thus satisfactory (Appendix 1). Average variance extracted was above 0.50 for the EB (0.54), PCE (0.66), and SV (0.54) scales, but remained slightly below this value for the EV scale (0.46). Because this latter value is close to 0.50, we conclude that although the EV scale showed some problems, convergent validity was not threatened. Discriminant validity was achieved with average variance extracted (AVE) for all constructs being higher than each construct’s highest square correlation with any other construct (Fornell and Larcker

1981) and all factor loadings being higher than all of their cross loadings. Finally, a series of confirmatory factor analyses using the covariance-based structural equation modelling software AMOS showed satisfying fit indices (Table 2). Specifically, RMSEA was below the cut-off value of 0.08 suggested by Browne and Cudeck (1992) for a reasonable fit, and CFI and TLI were above 0.90 (Bentler and Bonett, 1980).

[Place Table 2 About Here]

Environmental Consumer Segments

In order to identify consumer segments according to their ecological behaviors, we performed a two-stage cluster analysis (Punj and Steward 1983) using SPSS version 21.0. In a first step, we used Ward's hierarchical minimum variance method and opted for a five cluster solution based on an analysis of the dendograms and agglomeration schedules (Hair et al. 2009; Norusis, 2008). Specifically, the distance measures of the dendograms suggested the aggregation of relatively similar segments when moving from a six to a five cluster solution, but not when moving from a five to a four cluster solution. Further, the increase of the coefficients from the agglomeration schedule was large when moving from a five to a four cluster solution, but smaller when moving from a six to a five cluster solution, thus indicating the appropriateness of the five cluster solution. In a second step, we used a non-hierarchical K-means procedure to refine the clusters. Following Jurowski and Reich (2000), we validated the five-cluster solution by running a cluster analysis with a subset of 60% of the cases (429 respondents), randomly selected from the overall sample. The characteristics of the clusters from the reduced and the total sample were similar, suggesting a valid and generalizable cluster solution.

[Place Table 3 About Here]

The five segments identified in the cluster analysis can be described as follows (Table 3):

The first group of consumers, the non-ecological, is the largest group in the study, with 27.7% of the total. This group exhibits very limited behaviors towards reduction, reuse, recycling, and the purchase of environmentally friendly products. When compared to the other segments, the scale means in this group are the lowest of all environmental behaviors, indicating that they rarely exhibit the aforementioned behaviors. The second cluster, the eco-indifferent, represents 22% of the sample. This group concentrates particularly on reduction activities, but expresses little interest in reusing, recycling, or the purchase of environmentally friendly products. Thus, this segment seems to shy away from activities that require greater physical and economic commitment.

The third group of consumers is the eco-saver segment, which comprises 18.3% of the sample. This group displays environmental behaviors focused on reduction and reusing and, to a much lesser degree, recycling and consumption of ecologically friendly items. This unique combination of behaviors suggests that their environmentally friendly purchasing habits are related to the desire to save money through reduction in energy consumption and product reuse and repair. The fourth group is the eco-fashion consumer segment, which constitutes 15.2% of the sample. The most significant behaviors of this group are related to recycling and the purchase of environmentally friendly products. Conversely, the least frequent activities among the consumers belonging to this group are the reuse of products. This segment may be motivated by social trends and not necessarily by an intrinsic motivation to protect the natural environment. At the opposite end of the scale is the fifth segment, eco-integral consumers, which comprises 16.6% of the sample.

This segment exhibits the greatest commitment to all behaviors identified as benefiting the environment, with high rates of activity across the four dimensions (reuse, reduction, recycling, and the purchase of environmentally friendly products) of the EB scale.

Demographic Characteristics

A first step in characterizing the segments consists of relating demographic variables to the five consumer segments. The variables used in this analysis are gender, age, education, marital status, and income. Table 4 shows the results of the cross tables for each of the five demographic variables included in the analysis. The Chi-square distributions suggest significant differences between the segments for gender ($\chi^2=10.68$, $p<.05$), age ($\chi^2=62.58$, $p<.001$), education ($\chi^2=90.08$, $p<.001$), marital status ($\chi^2 =36.68$, $p<.001$), and income ($\chi^2=34.11$, $p<.01$).

[Place Table 4 About Here]

The eco-integral group includes slightly more women than men and their members demonstrate comparably high levels of education. The segment is relatively young (32.8% are between 18 and 25 years old) and has a high proportion of singles (49.2%). The eco-fashion group includes consumers with elevated levels of household income and education. This segment corresponds to an older age group (42.2% are 42 years or older) and has a lower proportion of singles (33.3%). They represent the most affluent group in the sample with 59.2% earning 11,600 pesos (USD 870) or more per month. The eco-saver segment (those consumers who focus on reducing and reusing rather than on recycling and the purchase of green products) has the highest percentage of women (62.6%) and the highest share of consumers earning less than 7,000 pesos (USD 520) per month (29.0%). The eco-

indifferent segment has the highest percentage of married consumers (55.8%). However, most of their demographic characteristics seem to represent an average of the population rather than extreme values. Finally, the non-ecological segment is made up of predominantly young (45.5% are between 18 and 25 years old) and single (55.0%) members. This segment is slightly biased towards male consumers (54.5%).

Environmental and Social Values and Perceived Consumer Effectiveness

In a second step, we analyzed how the five consumer segments differ across their perceived effectiveness of environmental actions as well as their environmental and social values. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) demonstrates significant differences between the sample means of the five segments (Table 5). Specifically, the non-ecological segment scores substantially lower than all other segments on the dimensions of altruism and openness to change. We thus argue that these two social values are important dimensions able to differentiate between consumers who exhibit pro-environmental behaviors and those who do not.

On the other hand, the eco-integral segment demonstrates the highest scores among all segments not only for the dimensions of altruism and openness to change, but also for conservatism and egoism. This result may appear surprising at first sight, given that intuitively, one might expect those consumers who care for the natural environment to be less egoistic than eco-indifferent or non-ecological consumers (Stern et al., 1999).

However, a closer inspection of the egoism subscale reveals that the scale items are predominantly related to a quest for wealth, power, and social influence, which are, especially in the context of an emerging economy such as Mexico, not necessarily opposed to environmentally friendly behaviors aimed at changing the planet.

[Place Table 5 About Here]

With respect to environmental values, an ANOVA based on the factor scores of the three EV subscales showed significant differences for anthropocentrism ($F(4, 710) = 4.79, p < .001$) and science & technocentrism ($F(4, 710) = 7.10, p < .001$), but not for biospherism ($F(4, 710) = 1.14, ns$). Specifically, the results suggest that the eco-fashion and eco-indifferent segments are the most anthropocentric groups, whereas the eco-savers and eco-integral are the least anthropocentric. Interestingly, those consumers who are the least confident in the advancements of science and technology are, in the Mexican context, the eco-integral. Finally, perceived consumer effectiveness showed statistically significant differences for the five consumer segments. Congruent with our expectations, the eco-integral segment was the highest in PCE ($m=3.99$) whereas the non-ecological segment scored lowest on this dimension ($m=3.38$). The results suggest that perceived environmental effectiveness is associated with the extent to which consumers engage in environmentally friendly behaviors and thus provide evidence in support of the external validity of our study.

DISCUSSION

The present study contributes to the literature on environmental segmentation and consumption in emerging markets by proposing a five-cluster segmentation of green consumers in the Mexican market. To our knowledge, this is the first systematic attempt to classify consumers and describe consumer segments on the basis of their environmental behaviors in a country from Latin America. We identified five distinct consumer segments

in Mexico based on their environmental behaviors. We described these segments as eco-indifferent, eco-fashion, eco-saver, eco-integral, and non-ecological. Four of these segments exhibit varying types and levels of environmental practices, whereas one segment (the non-ecological consumer) does not seem to engage much in any of the four environmental behaviors investigated in the study. Although some authors find that green consumption practices in emerging economies are generally not very developed (Carrete et al. 2012; Chan 2001; Mostafa 2007b), our research shows that there are consumers in Mexico who already adhere to environmentally friendly practices and who may be susceptible to messages, products, and services from green marketers and policy makers. However, our results suggest that pro-environmental behaviors in Mexico are not merely a question of adopting environmentally-friendly behaviors in general to a higher or lower extent. Rather, it is the combination of different environmental behaviors (such as the prevalence of recycling and the purchase of green products for the eco-fashion segment or the focus on reduction and reusing for the eco-saver segment) that provide important insights about the segments.

We also investigated the demographic characteristics, social values, environmental values, and level of perceived consumer effectiveness for the five segments. Consistent with previous studies (e.g., Roberts 1996; Samdahl and Robertson 1989), consumers exhibit significant differences in terms of gender, age, education, income, and marital status across the five segments. For example, whereas the eco-saver segment in our study is predominantly female (62.5%), the non-ecological segment is slightly biased towards male consumers (54.4%). Furthermore, the non-ecological segment has the highest proportion of consumers age 33 or lower (68.1%), whereas this percentage is 42.2% for the eco-active and 45.0% for the eco-savers. The environmentally conscious segment, the eco-integrals,

and the eco-fashions have the highest percentage of consumers with undergraduate or postgraduate studies (54.1% and 49.6%, respectively), whereas this percentage is significantly lower for the non-ecological group (23.2%). Interestingly, despite having a high level of education, the proportion of people with relatively high incomes (11,600 pesos per month or above) is lower for the eco-integrals (39.0%) than for other segments such as the non-ecological (46.4%) or eco-fashion segment (59.3%). Further, we find that the two segments representing the extreme poles in our study (that is, the eco-integral on one hand and the non-ecological on the other hand) are both substantially biased towards younger consumers. This result, in our opinion, reflects the reality in Mexico and other similar emerging economies of a dual society where some parts of the younger population are provided with great opportunities whereas other parts of society are left behind. Thus, our results suggest that in an emerging economy such as Mexico, the level of education rather than income may determine the extent to which consumers engage in environmentally friendly practices.

Our results further suggest that values are associated with environmentally friendly behaviors. For example, congruent with previous research (Stern et al. 1999; Straughan and Roberts 1999), we find that non-ecological consumers exhibit comparatively low levels of altruism and openness to change, whereas the eco-integrals score relatively high on these dimensions. Interestingly, the eco-integrals are also the most conservative and egoistic segment in our study. Combined, the results suggest that altruism, conservatism, and egoism are not necessarily the opposing endpoints of a latent underlying value, but rather should be seen as potentially complementary. Thus, environmental practices may be triggered not only by altruistic motives, but can be based as well on conservative and egoistic motivational forces. This finding is especially relevant in the context of emerging

economies, where consumers may still focus on satisfying their material needs and wants, and materialistic, self-centered values frequently dominate over altruistic or postmaterialist motives (Inglehart, 1990). We suggest that consumers in emerging economies may be motivated to engage in environmentally friendly behaviors not only based on messages to “save the planet” but also on messages that relate to an improvement in the individual’s quality of life.

We also find differences among segments with regard to environmental values. Congruent with previous research on the relationship between anthropocentrism and environmentally friendly behaviors (Nordlund and Garvill 2002; Thompson and Barton 1994), the eco-integral and eco-saver segments were the least anthropocentric in our study. On the other hand, the eco-fashion segment scored highest on anthropocentrism, supporting our notion that the comparably high levels of recycling and green product purchases for these consumers may be based on striving for social approval rather than a genuine concern for the natural environment. Our results further suggest that consumers who integrally engage in environmentally friendly behaviors are skeptical about the role of science and technology in society. Specifically, the eco-integral segment obtained the lowest scores on the scale items related to science and technocentrism, whereas the eco-fashion and eco-savers have comparably high scores on these value dimensions. Finally, the non-ecological segment exhibits low confidence toward the effectiveness of buying green products, whereas the other four segments score significantly higher on the two items of perceived effectiveness. As in prior studies (Straughan and Roberts 1999), perceived consumer effectiveness in this research captured the distinction between high- and low-ecological consumers. Specifically, non-ecological consumers scored significantly lower on the PCE scale than any of the other four segments. This finding suggests that attitudes about the natural

environment are related to environmentally-friendly behaviors and supports previous research (Awad 2011; Ellen et al. 1991; Oliver and Rosen 2010, Straughan and Roberts 1999) challenging the attitude-behavior gap in environmental consumption.

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

Our findings provide firms interested in the Mexican market with important insights about how to address consumers on the basis of their environmental behaviors. The current research also provides an estimate of the size of each segment, which may be useful for firms considering targeting one of these segments. In addition, our segmentation approach includes values and demographic descriptors, which make it easier for firms to identify and reach these segments. For instance, the demographic and value-based profiles of the five segments proposed in this research can be matched with media specific profiles to select the most appropriate mass media and other communication vehicles to reach consumers effectively.

The findings may assist marketing managers in making appropriate marketing mix decisions when targeting different consumer segments in emerging economies. For example, our research demonstrates that there is a market in Mexico for environmentally-friendly products and practices based on a genuine commitment to the natural environment. Although this segment, represented by the eco-integrals, is somewhat smaller (16.6%), it should be the most important target segment for green firms. Importantly, this segment is also the one that is most skeptical about the potential of science and technology to solve the environmental problems of this planet. Thus, marketers targeting this segment in Mexico may strive to avoid messages focusing on an excessive faith towards technology.

An interesting target for green products and recycling practices is also the eco-fashion segment; however, this segment seems to have high anthropocentric (as opposed to eco-centric) values and probably acquires green products for reasons different from those of the eco-integrals. Thus, when targeting the eco-fashion segment, marketers may try to emphasize the fashion or social approval aspect of recycling and green product consumption rather than an eco-centrally motivated concern for the environment. We further identify an eco-saver segment that seems to focus on reducing and reusing rather than on recycling and green products, and we assume that the environmentally friendly behavior of the eco-savers is largely based on frugality and the desire for a simple lifestyle. Marketers focusing on this segment could try to emphasize the resource and money-saving aspects of their products and services. For eco-indifferent segment, we suggest to place greater emphasis on generating awareness for the benefits of pro-environmental behaviors. Finally, due to their low levels of pro-environmental values and behaviors, the non-ecological is the least attractive segment for green marketers but the one that needs most attention from policy makers interested in improving environmentally-friendly consumption practices.

From a public policy point of view, the findings of this research may help governmental organizations and other policy makers to develop and target efforts aimed at informing and educating consumers about resource conservation, recycling, the consumption of green products, and environmental issues in general. Our findings suggest that a substantial portion of Mexican consumers do not engage significantly in any environmental practices. High anthropocentric values also prevail not only among non-ecological consumers, but also among the eco-indifferent and eco-fashion segments, suggesting that a major challenge

policy makers in Mexico face is achieving a genuine change in pro-environmental values and attitudes.

EXTERNAL VALIDITY, LIMITATIONS, AND FUTURE RESEARCH

In this section, we follow Winer's (1999) recommendation that empirical studies should generally discuss external validity and suspected boundary conditions, and that this discussion should appear in a section at the end of the research article. External validity concerns the question whether the results of a study would hold for other populations or research settings (Calder, Phillips, and Tybout 1982). Thus, Laurent (2000) suggests that before passing to the estimation or optimization stage, researchers should have a solid qualitative design based on classical qualitative methods such as in-depth interviews and observation. Our study follows these recommendations by building on an existing, qualitative framework of environmentally-friendly consumption in Mexico from Carrete et al. (2012). For example, our conclusion that the eco-fashion consumer segment in Mexico is driven by social approval rather than a genuine concern for the environment is informed by the qualitative research conducted by this group of authors. We argue that similar mechanisms should exist in many other emerging economies where consumers strive to emulate Western lifestyles from developed countries. However, threats to external validity certainly remain. For example, our segmentation is based on consumers from three large urban metropolitan areas. While several steps were taken to ensure the representativeness of the sample in relation to the three populations from which the sample was drawn, caution is advised when trying to generalize the results of the study to the entire country. For instance, our sample did not include consumers from rural areas, and it is possible that the research setting (urban vs. rural areas), as Lynch (1982) phrases it, is not free from

interaction effects with our variables of interest (environmentally-friendly behaviors, perceived consumer effectiveness, environmental values, and social values). An interaction effect between background variables such as the research setting with the variables of interest in this study would indeed indicate a threat to external validity.

Similar to previous research on green consumption (e.g., Cleveland, Kalamas, and Laroche 2005; Diamantopoulos et al. 2003; Fraj and Martinez 2006; Roberts and Bacon 1997; Schlegelmilch, Bohlen, and Diamantopoulos 1996), our study relies on self-reported environmental practices and thus may be biased because participants may have difficulty accurately recalling past behavior or because of social desirable responding. However, we strived to attenuate these potential problems by selecting scale items that were comparably easy to answer, by emphasizing the scientific (i.e., non-commercial) nature of the study, and by assuring the anonymity of participants.

Finally, our segmentation is based on a cross-sectional survey design. While this provides a useful snapshot of consumer groups based on their environmental behavior, consumers' environmental perspectives and practices are developing and evolving. This evolution of consumer perspectives underscores the need for a dynamic segmentation approach that considers consumers' evolving attitudes. For example, there is evidence that the consumer membership of a segment may be contingent on self-perception, with consumers moving in and out of segments as they try different identities (Dawes and Brown 2000; Gitlin 1989). Thus, future research may employ longitudinal studies to understand these changes.

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Table 1
Gender and Income Distribution for the Mexican Population and Sample

Characteristics	Percentage Population*	Percentage Sample
Gender		
Female	51.2%	50.8%
Male	48.8%	49.2%
Income		
Less than 7,000 pesos (USD 520)	25.0%	20.1%
7,000-11,599 pesos (USD 520-870)	35.8%	35.6%
11,600-34,999 pesos (USD 870-2,600)	32.0%	34.0%
35,000 pesos (USD 2,600) or higher	7.0%	9.9%

*INEGI (2010)

Table 2
Model Fit for Measurement Models from CFA

Fit Indices	Ecological Behaviors (EB)	Environmental Values (EV)	Social Values (SV)
CMIN	140.87	40.33	236.04
df	32	17	59
CMIN/df	4.40	2.37	4.00
CFI	.95	.97	.93
TLI	.93	.95	.91
RMSEA	.07	.04	.07

Note: Model fit indices for perceived consumer effectiveness (PCE) could not be calculated because two-item CFA models are underidentified in covariance-based structural equation modeling.

Table 3
Univariate Means and Descriptive Statistics for Five-Cluster Solution

Five-segment solution	N	Percent	Reduce	Reuse	Recycling and green product purchase
Non-ecological	198	27.7%	2.26	2.49	1.87
Eco-indifferent	158	22.1%	4.21	2.49	2.26
Eco-saver	131	18.3%	4.21	4.06	2.21
Eco-fashion	109	15.3%	3.87	2.70	3.47
Eco-integral	119	16.6%	4.16	4.35	3.91

Note: One-way ANOVAs for each variable were statistically significant. Reduce: $F(4, 714)=234.03, p<.001$; Reuse: $F(4, 714)=261.81, p<.001$; Recycling and green product purchase: $F(4, 714)=313.35, p<.001$.

Table 4
Demographics by Segment

	Non-ecological	Eco-indifferent	Eco-saver	Eco-fashion	Eco-integral	TOTAL	Chi-Square	Sig.
Gender							10.68	0.030
Male	54.5	52.5	37.4	51.4	47.1	49.2		
Female	45.5	47.5	62.6	48.6	52.9	50.8		
Age							62.58	.000
< 18	11.5	7.8	1.5	2.8	3.4	6.1		
18 a 25	34.0	22.1	20.6	22.0	32.8	26.8		
26 a 33	22.5	18.8	22.9	17.4	21.6	20.8		
34 a 41	14.7	13.0	16.0	15.6	12.9	14.4		
42 a 49	9.9	13.6	17.6	21.1	11.2	14.1		
50 a 58	4.7	12.3	14.5	14.7	14.7	11.4		
59 or over	2.6	12.3	6.9	6.4	3.4	6.3		
Education							90.08	.000
Elementary school	4.5	13.3	12.3	2.8	5.0	7.7		
Middle school	29.8	22.8	26.9	16.5	14.3	23.1		
High school	35.4	33.5	30.0	23.9	26.1	30.7		
Technical studies	20.7	25.9	22.3	44.0	45.4	29.8		
Undergraduate	2.5	1.3	1.5	10.1	4.2	3.5		
Postgraduate	0.5	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.8	0.4		
No studies	6.6	3.2	6.2	2.8	4.2	4.8	36.68	.000
Marital Status								
Single	55.9	35.9	34.1	33.3	49.2	42.9		
Married/Cohabiting	36.4	55.8	51.9	51.9	44.1	47.2		
Separated/Divorced	6.7	5.1	9.3	9.3	6.8	7.2		
Widow/er	1.0	3.2	4.7	5.6	0.0	2.7		
Incomes							34.11	.001
< 7,000 MXP	16.5	23.9	29.0	4.6	27.1	20.4		
7,000-11,599 MXP	37.1	36.8	32.8	36.1	33.9	35.6		
11,600-34,999 MXP	36.6	31.6	30.5	44.4	27.1	34.0		
35,000 or over MXP	9.8	7.7	7.6	14.8	11.9	10.1		

Note: Numbers below the segments indicate percentages.

Table 5
Perceived Consumer Effectiveness (PCE), Environmental Values (EV), and Social Values (SV) by Segment

	Non- Ecological	Eco- indifferent	Eco- saver	Eco- fashion	Eco- integral	F (4, 710)	Sig.
PCE	3.39	3.85	3.95	3.84	3.99	13.36	.000
EV							
Anthropocentrism	4.02	4.07	3.71	4.31	3.80	4.79	.001
Biospherism	4.18	4.24	4.21	4.22	4.28	1.14	.332
Science and Technocentrism	3.57	3.55	3.88	3.88	3.36	7.10	.000
SV							
Altruism	4.25	4.60	4.70	4.58	4.74	26.55	.000
Openness to Change	4.14	4.40	4.43	4.52	4.50	11.26	.000
Conservatism	3.22	3.17	3.15	3.13	3.49	2.85	.035
Egoism	3.48	3.66	3.65	3.32	4.07	8.37	.012

Note: Numbers in the Table indicate scores on five-point measurement scales.